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Dissertation**

**ANALYSIS OF RURAL SETTLEMENTS EXPANSION PATTERN:
A Case Study of Sachibunia Village Under Batiaghata Upazila in Khulna District**

**FEBRUARY
2006**

ANALYSIS OF RURAL SETTLEMENTS EXPANSION PATTERN:

A Case Study of Sachibunia Village Under Batiaghata Upazila in Khulna District

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DISSERTATION

FEBRUARY, 2006

**URBAN AND RURAL PLANNING DISCIPLINE
SCIENCE, ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY SCHOOL
KHULNA UNIVERSITY, KHULNA- 9208
BANGLADESH**

DEDICATED TO

My Beloved Late Grand-Father

Acknowledgement

First of all, praises belong to God, the most merciful, most kind and generous to man and his action. Then, I articulate my deep gratitude to my parents and my family who are standing in my mind at every where and every moment.

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Sujit Kumar Sikder

ABSTRACT

Usually settlements grow with the increase of population. The word ‘settlements’ denotes a village where a group of people have come to live and make their homes, usually where few or no people lived before. It is conspicuous that settlements are not only the built up part made by man, but all the space–natural or man-made, used by man. Expansion of rural settlement means human behaviours that are created as a physical environment on an area. Physical environment can be treated as settlement form and pattern or chronological area coverage.

Bangladesh, with an agrarian socio-economic base, is dominated by a rural settlement structure. About 76.61% populations live in rural Bangladesh. Land pressures and land use conflicts are seen in rural Bangladesh. Because, Horizontal expansion is very common than vertical expansion. Land resource is limited. Land man ratio is only 26 decimal in Bangladesh. Expansion of the rural settlements make more pressure on the agriculture and the agricultural land is decreasing. The settlements expansion guidelines are necessary for the optimum utilisation of limited land resources in rural areas of Bangladesh.

In Sachibunia village the settlement has been expanding rapidly for last fifteen years. Here the settlement area is increasing rapidly due to some responsible factors. The present study has analysed the responsible factors of settlement expansion under following categories: a) Demographic, b) Physical, c) Economic, d) Socio-political and e) Environmental. The development of Rupsha by pass road plays a great impact for the expansion of settlement. The establishment of Khulna University and other institutions lead the growth trend of Khulna city towards south-west direction have also some influence on expansion of settlement in Sachibunia village.

Rapid settlements expansion make more pressure on agricultural land. So it is necessary to manage the expansion of settlements in a planned way.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviations

BURP	Bachelor of Urban and Rural Planning
BWDB	Bangladesh Water Development Board
BBS	Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics
CS	Cadastral Survey
CF	Cumulative Frequency
CBD	Central Business District
etc	Etceteras
FAR	Floor Area Ratio
GOB	Government of Bangladesh
GIS	Geographical Information System
HH	Household
HBB	Haring Bon Bond
KU	Khulna University
KDA	Khulna Development Authority
KCC	Khulna City Corporation
LGED	Local Government and Engineering Department
LGRD	Local Government and Rural Development
NGO	Non-government Organization
RS	Revisional Survey
RD	Rural Development
SSI	Semi-structured Questionnaire
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
SA	State Acquisition
UP	Union Parisad

Acronyms

i.e.	That is
km	Kilometre
kg	Kilogram
No.	Number
TK.	Taka
%	Percentage

GLOSSARY

Bazar: Type of market where local product are sold.

Katcha road: Unpaved Road.

Katcha house: For research work katcha house was defined as house which roof is made of Golpata, thatch and wall is made of mud, wood, bamboo stick and bamboo mat. Mouza: Smallest revenue unit.

Pacca road: Paved road.

Pacca House: The pacca house was defined as house which roof is made of concrete and wall is made of brick.

Semi-Pacca House: The semi-pacca house was defined as house which roof is made of tin, tiles and wall's materials are brick and wood.

Upazila: Administrative unit above Union and below district level.

Union: Lowest administrative unit in Bangladesh which comprises of several villages.

Village: A geo-social entity.

Van: Non-motorised three wheeler vehicle used as local transport mode.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Bangladesh, with an agrarian socio-economic base, is characterised primarily by a rural settlement structure. The word “rural” comes from the Latin word “Ruralisrus” which is equivalent with English word “the country”. Similarly the word “settlement” comes from the English word “sett” meaning “Seat” or “setlan” (Mhamud: 1997: 8). Expansion of rural settlement means human behaviours that are created as a physical environment in rural area. Physical environment can be treated as settlement form and pattern or chronological area coverage.

About 76.61 percent people live in rural area of Bangladesh (BBS: 2001: 6). Conservation of rural living environment is very necessary for rural people. The original vegetation cover has been lost and the basic landscape has been changed considerably by levelling, tracing of land and also irrigation practices, and they have derived their characters from the pattern of human settlements development, homestead rising, pond construction for domestic water supply and agriculture (Sultana: 1993: 29).

Land resource is limited and land man ratio is only 26 decimal in Bangladesh (Daily Itafaq: 09.04.2005). Land pressures and land use conflict is always continuing in rural Bangladesh, Horizontal expansion is very common than vertical expansion. For the expansion of the rural settlement make more pressure on the agricultural land in the rural area, the agricultural land is decreasing.

Population growth is the main cause of indiscriminate settlement expansion. Most agricultural lands are converting into the small homestead units. Because, the joint families of the rural area are converting to single units and they need separate space for living. So, more and more lands are converting as settlement. Finally, for haphazard expansion of rural settlements - the cultivable lands are decreasing and affecting agricultural production day by day,

Now a days, it is necessary to guide the settlement expansion in a rational way both for rural and urban area. Especially for the rural area, the settlement expansion guidelines are necessary for the optimum utilisation of limited land resources.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of the study are:

- ☑ To explore the trend of settlement expansion from 1971 to 2005 in the study area.
- ☑ To identify the responsible factors of settlements expansion in the study area.

1.3 LITERATURE REVIEW

There is ample literature on rural settlement expansion issue. Some of the relevant literature, both published and unpublished is reviewed to identify the knowledge gap.

A) Ms. Sabiha Sultana (1993) in her book “*Settlements in Bangladesh: Spatial Pattern and Development*” provides an idea about rural settlements. She evaluates the character, regional variation, spatial variation, controlling factor, and policy guideline of rural settlement. She pointed out that most of the rural settlements have grown only for natural factors and the density of settlement is high (Sultana: 1993: 23, 24 & 67). But all the aspects of her study are conducted at macro scale. The settlement expansion trend, responsible factors and effects are not so clear, especially at local context.

B) Mr. Md. Emranul Haq (1996) in his BURP thesis “*Land Use Analysis of Village: A Study of Chakundia Village, Dumuria Thana, Khulna*” analyse the land use pattern of a village and its impact of the socio-economic characteristics. He identified that the rural settlement expansion have a great impact on the rural land use change. He showed that in 1974 total population of Chunkundia village was 1338 with total cultivable land of 329 acre. But in 1990 total amount of cultivable land stands only 300 acre (Haq: 1996: 42). But he did not quantify the impact. Moreover, discussion on the responsible factors of rural settlement expansion is absent.

C) Mr. V. Skouratovski (1971) in his reports “*Planning and Development of Rural Settlements: Part-I and Part-II*” discussed about overall picture of rural settlements, general statements concerning the methods and forms of planning rural areas and rural settlement, organizational, financial and administrative problems of planning and development of rural areas (Skouratovski: 1971: 2). Study has been relating to the development of rural areas in Austria, Belgium, Denmark, the Federal republic of Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden. The rural characteristics of Europe and Bangladesh may not same.

D) Mr. Abdul Baqee (1998) in his book “*Rural Settlement*” discuss about rural settlements. In the first chapter he reviewed different documents about the formation of rural settlements. In second chapter and seventh chapter described different types of settlement and in eleventh chapter about the planning of rural settlement. He identified some problems of rural settlement planning. Those are physical legal, socio-economic and finally implanted problems (Baqee: 1998: 6 & 570). All the discussions about rural settlements were concerned at macro level and the local issues are ignored. Here it is not mentioned that what are the factors responsible for settlement expansion.

By all the reviewed literature, it is identified that the rural settlement expansion pattern is very important for physical planning in the rural area and socio-economic development of rural population. Those literature covered macro level and did not satisfy the local context. Thus the present study provides a research gap and it is dealt with the study of rural settlement in the country with special attention to analyse the trend of rural settlement expansion and identify the responsible factors of settlement expansion from 1971 to 2005.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study is a dissertation conducted by a student of URP of Khulna University on settlement expansion in Sachibunia village. The study has some scope. They are as follows-

- ❑ The study takes an opportunity to sort out the trend of settlement expansion in the study area in last 35 years.
- ❑ The periodical change of infrastructure is represented with explanation the relation between infrastructural change and settlement expansion.
- ❑ The trend of socio economic status of the settlers like- occupational status, family income, educational status etc. are discussed.
- ❑ The study has identified the responsible factors for rapid expansion of settlement in the study area.

1.5 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

From the beginning of the study, it was faced various kinds of problems. The major limitations of the study are as follows-

- ❑ The study is based on field survey. During survey, respondents often provided misleading information related to year of homestead establishment, reason for homestead establishment, etc. This misleading information created some problems in data analysis and interpretation. This ultimately delayed reporting.
- ❑ The updated CS (Cadastral Survey) map was not available in the study area or Collectorate Record Room of Khulna.
- ❑ Due to lack of accurate information, out migration was not studied specially Hindu families who left the village for India.
- ❑ The periodical changes of settlement quality in terms of FAR, spacing, vertical expansion, building materials have not been extensively discussed.

1.6 CONCEPTS AND DEFINITIONS

- ❑ **Rural Area:** Rural area is that where maximum population are depend on agriculture and the service facilities are less and the population density is very low. The primary occupations of the inhabitants are mostly agricultural activities.
- ❑ **Settlement:** Settlement is a place where people come to live and constructed their homes and where few or no people lived before.
- ❑ **Settlement pattern:** Pattern of settlement indicates the geometrical arrangement of a large number of settlements and is applicable to a set of large number of rural settlement. Density may be divided as low, moderate, high.

CHAPTER TWO: STUDY AREA

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The Sachibunia village, Khulna has been selected as the study area for conducting the present study. Sachibunia village is located at Batiaghata Upazila in Khulna district. The study area can be represented by Sachibunia Mouza (sheet no. 3) of Jalma union. The Sachibunia village is one of the prominent Village of the Jalma union. In this village, about 146 families are living in 2005.

2.2 LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA

The Batiaghata Upazila consists of seven unions, wherein Jalma union is located in the North part of the Upazila. The Jalma union is located at the last north part of the Batiaghata Upazila surrounded by Khulna sadar Upazila on the north, Dumuria Upazila on west, Batiaghata union (Batiaghata Upazila) on south-west, Baliadanga union on south-east. The Sachibunia village is one of the prominent Village of the Jalma union. The village is located on the extreme northern part of the union. The location of the study area is represented by map 2.1.

Sachibunia village is at distance of about 5 km from Khulna district headquarter. Transportation cost of van from study area to Moylapota of Khulna city is taka 4 to 6 per person and takes time about 10 to 15 minutes. It also located within polder no 28/2. So the area is protected from saline water and flood.

2.3 SOIL

Soil is the basic factor in the study of settlement expansion pattern. The study area is apparently a flat alluvial plain with apparent homogenous land and soil condition. In the study area, the soils are mainly silty clay due to the Ganges tidal flood plains.

2.4 CLIMATE

Climate is one of the principal aspects for settlement formation. The study area has a humid, warm and tropical climate which is fairly uniform throughout the district. There are three main seasons:

- 1) A hot summer season with high humidity from March to June.
- 2) A hot and humid monsoon with heavy rainfall from June to October, and,
- 3) A relatively cool and dry winter season from November to March.

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2.5 IMPORTANT FEATURES

A list of important features and infrastructure of the study area is given below-

Table 2.1: Important establishments of the study area

Establishments	Number
Primary school	1
High school	1
Hat/Bazar	2
Temple	2
Rice mill	3

Source: Field survey, 2005

2.6 TRANSPORTATION AND COMMUNICATION

It is well connected with the Khulna district headquarter and Upazila headquarter by Gallamalri-Batiaghata road. The basic means of transport available in the study area are non-motorised vehicles, tempo and bus. Van plays a vital role in local transportation. There is about 1 km metalled and about 0.5 km HBB roads in the study area. The villagers get communication facilities mobile, telephone at Sachibunia and Dargatala bazar.

2.7 DEMOGRAPHIC SCENARIO

In the study area majority male people i.e. 24.3 % belong to the 0-14 age group. And the average of 0-14 age population is 48% because of higher population growth rate. The male female ratio in the study area is 100:97. In this study more than 13% people are aged above 50 years. They are interviewed in this study.

2.8 OCCUPATION AND INCOME PATTERN

Among the people who settled before 1981, farming was the principal occupation. Since 1991 the occupational and income pattern were being changing because the impact of Khulna city. Most of the families' income level is between TK.4000-8000. Most of the people are involved non-farm occupations like construction, transportation and communication, business, services and others. There are also reasons behind the rapid expansion of settlement by the people who are involved in non-farm occupation. In Appendix-D, in Table D1 and D2 show the occupation and income pattern of the settlers respectively.

2.9 EDUCATIONAL STATUS

In the following table the educational level of the household head according to their year of homestead establishment.

Table 2.2: Educational status of the household heads

Education level	Year of settlement establishment					Total
	Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05	
Signature only	6	2	1	4	3	16
Primary	23	10	14	13	8	68
Secondary	1	0	1	4	6	12
S.S.C	0	1	2	3	1	7
H.S.C	2	0	1	4	2	9
Degree	1	2	0	4	4	11
Degree +	0	0	1	4	2	7
MBBS	0	0	0	1	0	1
Illiterate	6	7	1	1	0	15
Total	39	22	21	38	26	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

In this study apart from academic qualification, those who able to sign were also considered as literate. Here it is found that more than 50% of household head are taken only primary education. Most of them are settled before 1971. The higher educated people started to settle in this area after 1991.

2.10 HOUSEHOLD SIZE

The following table shows the house size of the settlers with respected of their year of homestead establishment.

Table 2.3: House hold size of the settlers

HH size	Year of homestead establishment										Total	
	Before 1971		1971-80		1981-90		1991-2000		2001-05			
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Below 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5.3	2	7.7	4	2.7
4	2	5.1	0	0	3	14.3	7	18.4	7	26.9	19	13
5	13	33.3	8	36.4	13	61.9	18	47.4	12	46.2	64	43.8
6	8	20.5	8	36.4	3	14.3	6	15.8	5	19.2	30	20.5
7	7	17.9	5	22.7	0	0	4	10.5	0	0	16	11
8	5	12.8	1	4.5	0	0	1	2.6	0	0	7	4.8
Above 8	4	10.3	0	0	2	9.5	0	0	0	0	6	4.1
Total	39	100	22	100	21	100	38	100	26	100	146	100

Source: Field survey, August 2005

The settlers' average household size is 5.8. No. of joint families is in this village only 33. A family of 18 members was found in the village.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

Methodology is a logical as well as systematic part of the study to guide scientific investigation. The methodological steps for the present study are discussed below-

3.1 CONCEPTUALISATION

After finishing a set of courses on rural planning, the concept of the current research work has been developed. The several articles from newspapers, conversation with knowledgeable person also helped to formulate concept. Finally, the rural settlement expansion pattern (which is far below the satisfactory level) influenced to conceptualise the present work.

3.2 PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

After conceptualisation; some research questions were developed and the problem of the study has been clearly defined. In that context of rural settlement expansion pattern, the trend of settlement expansion and its responsible factors has been set up as objectives of the study.

3.3 SELECTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The study area was selected as Sachibunia village under Batiaghata Upazila. There have some causes for this selection. They are-

- ❑ Easy accessibility
- ❑ Located near the university so that extensive land use and questionnaire survey have been conducted easily
- ❑ Some relevant data were available in the seminar library of URP

3.4 RECONNAISSANCE SURVEY

In order to attain a pre-knowledge and overview of the village, a reconnaissance survey was conducted in the study area. It helps to develop an appropriate questionnaire and to finalizing the survey technique procedure. From the primary field visit overall perspective of the village was extracted.

3.5 QUESTIONNAIRE PREPARATION

Appropriate questionnaires have been prepared for collecting necessary primary information from the field. An open ended even in some cases close ended question have been set upon that questionnaire according to its necessity. At first a draft questionnaire have been prepared and pretested in the field. Then the final questionnaires have been prepared. In the current study a census survey have been conducted with all well designed questionnaire covering aforementioned indicators. The questionnaires are enclosed (Appendix-A).

3.6 DATA COLLECTION

Two types of data have been collected for this study. The data, which have collected from the direct survey, is called primary data and which have collected from different organizations, books, researches, journals etc. is called secondary data.

3.6.1 Primary data collection: After preparation and testing of the questionnaire, determination survey plan; the primary information has been collected through direct field investigation, land use survey as well as discussion with the aged people and by observation. In the current study a lot of primary information has been collected, such as settlement expansion trend, causal factors of settlement expansion, effect of settlement expansion on agricultural land.

3.6.2 Secondary data collection: In this stage, the secondary information has been collected from both governments and non-government organizations. The attributes that have been collecting from the secondary sources described as mouza map, land use map, demographic data, different approaches of rural settlement planning and others.

3.7 LIST OF INDICATORS

For the study both primary and secondary data have been collected from different sources/respondents.

Different sources of information

Objectives	Required Data	Indicators	Data type	Respondent /document
Objective 1	Settlement	▶ Houses establishment date	P+S	Aged respondent,
		▶ Settlement expansion type		Maps (CS/SA/RS,
		▶ Density, pattern		LGED maps), Field survey
	Land use	Land cover	▶ Land cover	P
▶ Type of land				
Land use		▶ Infrastructure map	S	LGED, Thana land
		▶ Mouza map		record office, LGRD, Local Amin
Objective 2	Demographic	▶ Population pressure	P+S	BBS, UP, Field survey
		▶ No of household		
		▶ Family size, age structure		
	Economic	▶ Economic activity base	P+S	Aged respondent,
		▶ Agricultural production		Field survey,
		▶ Land value		Relevant document/Study
Natural	▶ Disaster, River line	P+S	Organizational standard, others documents	
	▶ Environmental effect ▶ Climate, natural			
Social	▶ Social norms, Religion	P+S	Questionnaire survey	
	▶ culture, marital status			
Geographical		▶ Topography	P+S	Field survey & others
		▶ Land height		
		▶ Distance from growth centre/service centre		
		▶ Location of river/canal		

P = Primary, S = Secondary, P+S = Primary + Secondary

3.8 METHOD OF RESEARCH

Different research methods as well as tools/techniques have been used for the study, considering the data sources, required information/data and their nature.

Research methods and techniques

Research method/tools	Description	Document/Respondent/organization
Documentary analysis/Literature review	Identification research gap Concept of rural settlement Trend of settlement growth	Different books, journals, website, publish reports and documents
Reconnaissance	Overall study area, Views of the concern agencies, Rural development practice, KDA master plan, component of settlement, causal factors of settlement expansion, service facility of the dwellers, rural development initiatives, Demographic structure, Economic structure, Environmental factors, Land value	Union parisad, KDA, LGED,LGRD,BWDB, Upazila parisad, Rural development experts, Environmental expert, Members, different NGO's, concern persons of these institutions and the local people
Observation and interview		
Land use and infrastructure survey	Rural land use, Physical dimension of rural settlement and their changes, embankment, market location, roads, culvert, sludge gate, river, canal etc	The local people, LGED, land survey department Direct field survey,
SSI, Key informants	Settlement structure, knowledge about settlement expansion, knowledge about causal factor of settlement expansion, asses the effect of settlement expansion	RD experts, Environmental expert, Local people, Inhabitants of the study area
Open discussion		
Focus group discussion	To assess the public mentality, identify threats, gather knowledge about human behaviour pattern, identify problems	Villagers, Farmers, Old people, Local leader, land owners
Household survey	Identify trend of settlement expansion, identify causal factor of settlement expansion, Effect on agricultural production, About service facility.	Aged villagers, Census survey will be conducted for HH survey.

3.9 CO-ORDINATION SCHEMA

The coordination schema was developed with considering all the parameters; indicators/variables and their measuring unit for the study. Here a structure of the study was presented. It was performed effective role for research work. It is enclosed (Appendix-B) in detail.

3.10 DATA ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND PRESENTATION

Collected all the data/information both spatial and non-spatial have been organized, explained and analysed by different planning and statistical tools/techniques.

Planning and Statistical Tools/techniques for Analysis

ANALYTICAL TOOLS/TECHNIQUES	DESCRIPTION/APPLICATION
GIS: ARC INFO, ARC VIEW, ArcGIS	For analysing the data from physical survey/land and infrastructure survey
GIS: ARC INFO, ARC VIEW, ArcGIS	For creating and presenting thematic maps (previous and post/existing condition)
SPSS	For analysing the statistical data from field survey, observation survey and others
Power point	For seminar presentation
Microsoft word and Excel	For thesis presentation i.e. text, facts, graphs and figures

Figure 3.1: Flowchart of the methodology

CHAPTER FOUR: TREND OF SETTLEMENT EXPANSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Settlements are growing with increase of population. In the study area during the earlier period the settlements were formed by farmer families. At the beginning, the area of the settlement was very small. Sachibunia settlement has been expanding fast for last fifteen years. A rapid expansion of settlement has been taken place in this period. The trend of settlement expansion of this village can be described by some indicators. The indicators are trend of homestead establishment, growth rate, housing density, land use change.

4.2 TREND OF HOMESTEAD ESTABLISHMENT

New homestead establishment indicates the expansion of settlement. This can shown by the following table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Trend of homestead establishment from 1971 to 2005

Year	Increase	Number of homestead
Before 1971	-	39
1971-80	22	61
1981-90	21	82
1991-2000	38	120
2001-05	26	146

Source: Field survey, 2005.

Table 4.1 shows the trend of homestead establishment from 1971 to 2005. It presents that in 1971, total number of homestead was only 39, but in 2005 it becomes 146 in number. There was a rapid increase in the number of homestead establishment from early 1990s.

4.3 TREND OF GROWTH RATE

In the following figure 4.1 shows the average annual growth rate of the housing unit in different decades/periods is presented.

Figure 4.1: Average annual growth rate (Housing unit per year)

The average annual growth rates are estimated by dividing the increased number of housing unit with respective years. It is found that the annual growth rate at 1971-80 is lower that is only 2.2 and 1981-90 almost same that is 2.14. But from the beginning of 1991 it is raised faster. During the period 2001-05 the growth rate is 5.2 per year.

4.4 TREND OF HOUSING DENSITY

The housing density indicates the quality and spatial arrangement of settlement. The housing density of Sachibunia village is presented by the following figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Housing density (Housing unit per acre)

Source: Field survey, 2005

Here, the housing density is calculated as dividing the total number of housing unit by total homestead area. In 1970s the housing density was only 7 unit per acre. But in 1980s and 1990s the housing density was same that is 8 unit per acre. In 2005 the housing density is high. Because new homesteads are established in the area.

4.5 TREND OF LAND USE CHANGE

Settlements and land use are interrelated with each other, because settlements are developed on the land and creates a geometrical shape with aggregate of some housing elements likes houses, roads, and others functions.

Table 4.2: Status of land use in the study area

Year	Home stead area (acre)			Agricultural land+ others (acre)
	Increase	Increase rate/year	Cumulative	
1970	-	-	5.12	149.88
1980	2.33	0.23	7.45	147.55
1990	2.19	0.22	9.64	145.36
2000	3.47	0.35	13.11	141.89
2005	2.16	0.44	15.27	139.73

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table 4.2 shows the status of land use in the study area. The total land area of this village (Mouza) is about 155 acres. In 1971 the settlements area was only about 5.12 acres. Agricultural and other lands were about 149.88 acres. But after 35 years, the settlements area becomes about 15.27 acres. But agricultural and other lands are about 139.73. So it is clear that rapid expansion of settlement area. The increase of homestead area and decrease of agricultural area also indicate expansion of settlement. In 1980s, increase rate of homestead area was only 0.23 acres and the growth rate of housing unit was only 2.14. But in 2005, increase rate of homestead area was 0.44 acre, but the growth rate of housing unit was 5.2. See (Appendix D) for more detail.

Rural settlements are depending upon the population increase. Population growth is grained by birth rate, migration rate and it brings the direct effect on the agricultural land coverage. The settlement expansion has a close relation with the change of land use. The periodical changes of land use composition are shown by the following figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 Trend of land use change

Source: Field survey, 2005

Here, it is clear that the agricultural land is decreasing day by day. But, the homestead and other (like-road, school, market etc) land use are increasing simultaneously. It indicates that the expansion of settlement have a pressure on agricultural lands.

The land use pattern is presented by the map 4.1 and map 4.2. Map 4.1 is represented the land use pattern in 1971 and the map 4.2 represented the land use pattern in 2005.

4.6 SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF SETTLEMENT EXPANSION

A ribbon/linear type of settlement is developed in the study area. This pattern of settlement is continued. But the concentration is more at eastern and western portion of the village. They also signify the periodical expansion pattern of settlement. The changes of physical infrastructure are clearly identified by maps 4.4, 4.5, 4.6 and 4.7. According to the maps, the settlements expansion pattern are illustrate below-

4.6.1 Pattern of settlement expansion during 1971 to 1980:

The settlement expansion patterns during 1971 to 1880 are shown by the map 4.4. Here it is found that the settlement of Sachibunia is linearly expanded. At earlier period the settlements were less dense. Most of the settlers were prefer the land near farm lands for homestead establishment. In this period the settlements were formed at the eastern and western part of the village.

4.6.2 Pattern of settlement expansion during 1981 to 1990:

The settlement expansion patterns during 1971 to 1880 are shown by the map 4.5. In this period the Khulna-Batiaghata road was developed as *pacca*. Then, the settlement was expanded indiscriminately. In this period more expansion were take place in eastern side and middle portion of the village. The settlers whose occupation was farming; they were settled in middle portion and whose occupations were non-farming; they were settled at the eastern portion of the village.

4.6.3 Pattern of settlement expansion during 1991 to 2000:

During this period the settlements were grown more at the eastern portion of the village. As the new settlers were settled near Sachibunia *bazar*. Most of the settlers' were lower and middle income people from Muslim community (See Appendix-D, table D2 and D3). For development of Sachibunia-Ninhkhamar road a large number of city dwellers were come to this area and they were established homestead beside Sachibunia-Ninhkhamar road. The features are shown by the map 4.6.

4.6.4 Pattern of settlement expansion during 2000 to 2005:

During this period the settlement was also developed at the eastern portion of the village. In this period, all the agricultural lands at the eastern sides are covered by the homestead area. The lower and middle income people wanted to settle here. Because the land value comparatively affordable than Khulna city (See Appendix-D, table D15). The settlement expansion is shown by the map 4.7.

Map 4.5: Village Sachaibunia: Settlement expansion from 1981 to 1990

Map 4.6: Village Sachaibunia: Settlement expansion from 1991 to 2000

Map 4.7: Village Sachaibunia: Settlement expansion from 2000 to 2005

Map 4.8: Village Sachaibunia: Some important features

4.7 Housing condition of the settlers’:

The quality of settlement is changeable. The quality of settlement depends upon various factors. The housing type is one of them.

Table 4.3 Housing type in the study area

House type	Year of homestead establishment					Total
	Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05	
Building	0	0	1	2	2	5
Semi-pacca	0	0	2	6	4	12
Katcha	37	22	20	30	20	129
Total	39	22	21	38	26	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table 4.9 shows that most of the houses were *katcha*. But after 1980s some houses were built as semi-pacca and building. So the quality of settlement improved.

4.8 CONCLUSION

From the discussion it is clear that a ribbon type of settlement pattern is formed in the study area. Before 1971 the people were settled at the western and middle portion of the village because of the tendency of the farmer to live near their farm land. But after 1981, the new dwellers mostly urban, started to settle on eastern part of the village. Because the settlers wanted to take advantage of Khulna city and Sachibunia bazar. During 1990 to 2005 most of the settlers come from out side the study area. In this period, most of the settlers’ established their homestead on agricultural lands (See Appendix D, table D5). Because most of the settlers needed to communicate with Khulna city. The study area is predominantly a Hindu area. But the new settlers’ are mostly from Muslim community. The preferred land for homestead establishment, occupational status, family income level, religious status, source of land for homestead establishment, agricultural land ownership pattern are shown in the Appendix-D. In the next chapter, the responsible factors for settlement expansion have been illustrated.

CHAPTER FIVE: RESPONSIBLE FACTORS FOR SETTLEMENT EXPANSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

From the discussion of previous chapter, it is clear that a rapid expansion of settlement in Sachibunia village is ongoing. Now it is necessary to explore what are responsible factors of settlement expansion. The determinants for settlement expansion are population density, settlement locations, housing structure, transportation and communication network, community development and infrastructure. It is also found that when a new road constructed then the settlement is expanded along it. The cause for this type of expansion to get more accessibility. For fulfilment of the second objective, in this chapter tried to identify the responsible factors for settlement expansion.

5.2 RESPONSIBLE FACTORS

Settlement expansion depends on different factors. The responsible factors for settlement expansion may be as like- demographic, physical, economic, socio-political environmental etc.

Figure 5.1: Status of responsible factors for settlement expansion

Source: Field survey, 2005

All the responsible factors are categorized into five broad classes according to their characteristics. The classes are i) Demographic, ii) Physical, iii) Economic, iv) Socio-political and v) Environmental.

Percentile distribution of different factors for settlement expansion – Demographic, Physical, Economic, Socio-political and Environmental are 8, 24, 27, 21 and 20 percent respectively. Among them economic and physical factors are more responsible for settlement expansion in the study area.

5.3 STATUS OF RESPONSIBLE FACTORS BASED ON PERIOD

The following figure 5.2 illustrates the comparative picture of different responsible factors in different period.

Figure 5.2: Responsible factors for settlement expansion in different year

Source: Field survey, 2005

Here, it is clear that from 1971-80 the demographic factors were more prominent. The socio-political and environmental factors were equally responsible for settlement expansion from 1971 to 1980. The economic and physical factors were got less importance in this period. From 1981-90 also the demographic factors were more prominent and the others factors were getting mostly equal responsible for settlement expansion in Sachibunia village. During the period from 1991 to 2000 the physical, economic factors were very strong. In this period this two type of factors were major. In the year range, from 2000 to 2005 the physical factors were getting more importance. See (Appendix-D, Table D8) for more detail.

5.3.1 Demographical factors:

The demographic factors are important implication for the expansion of settlement. The natural expansion of settlement takes place by demographic factors. Under demographic factors two aspects were found- a) Increase in the number of family members and household size and b) In migration.

Two factors are found in the study, they are-

a) Increase in the number of family members and household size: The household size naturally increases along with the population growth, increase adult population, new birth, and marriage. Ultimately, it leads towards the formation of new families as well as new housing units. As a result new housing area expands and thus settlement expansion occurs.

b) In migration: In the village in migration is an important demographic factor for settlement expansion. Most of the migrants came from Dakop, Koyra and Batiaghata Upazila. The causes of migration were river erosion and loss of their previous house.

Here, 38% settlers origins were others area. Others area includes Dakop, Satkhira, Dumria, Bagahat, Jessore etc.

The city dwellers are started to settle more during 1991 to 2005 due to enormous development of transport sector. About 21% settlers' came from Batiaghata. Before 1971 a large number of settlers were come from

Figure 5.3 Origin of the settlers'

Batiaghata most of them were farmer. More detailed information are attach in the Appendix-D, Table D15.

5.3.2 Physical factors:

The physical factors are very prominent factor for expansion of settlement in Sachibunia village. The factors are presented by the following figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: Percentile distribution of different physical factors for settlement

Source: Field survey, 2005

a) Land available for housing: In the study area the housing lands are available. Because, it is located in polder no-28/2. The lands are also flood free and suitable for housing. About 32% respondents opined on behalf of this factor.

b) Near to city: The distance of Khulna headquarter is only 5km from the village. The travel cost is 3 to 5 taka and takes time about 10 to 15 minutes. So it is a suitable location for settlers. This factor gets 30% weight from respondents.

c) Availability of transport: The Batiaghata-Gollamary highway connects the village with Khulna city. The transport modes like van, rickshaw, tempo, bus are available here. For this factor 19% of the people was settle in the area. From 1981 to 2005 the factor is predominant. Because, Batiaghata-Gollamary highway developed in 1983, 1 km of Sachibunia-Nechkhamer road paved in 1985 and 0.5 km developed as HBB in 1997.

d) Proximity to working place: The factor is responsible in earlier period and also today. Because in earlier period most of the people were farmer and their farm land were within 5 to 6 minutes walking distance. Today most of the settlers work in Khulna city which is also close from the village.

There are also some physical factors like- good infrastructure facilities, proximity to service centres, land acquired for by pass road. See Appendix-D, Table D10.

5.3.3 Economic factors:

The economic factors are growing and diversifying despite the notable declines in traditional economic sectors. Changes in economic dependence indicate an economic transformation based on new sources of income. The economic factors are given by the following figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Percentile distribution of different economic factors for settlement

Source: Field survey, 2005

a) Low land value: Among economic factors this factor is prominent and 37% respondents opined for this. This factor was very strong from 1991 to 2005. Comparatively the land value is low in the study area (See Appendix D, Table D14). So, the low income and middle income people want to settle in this area. Almost this people are working in Khulna city.

b) Land available for farming: This factor affected settlement expansion before 1980s. Then some people came from Batiaghata and Satkhira to Sachibunia for this reason.

c) Low travel time and cost: The distance of Khulna headquarter is only 5km from the village and transport modes are available here. Transportation cost of van from study area to Moylapota of Khulna city is taka 3 to 5 per person and takes time about 10 to 15 minutes. For low travel time and cost the settlers of this village can move easily.

d) For better income: Along with the expansion of settlement and increase in population some job opportunities are emerged, specially some rural service and small retail business. Moreover, Migrates are found the possibilities of better economic opportunities in the area than their previous places.

Without these economic factors there is another factor that is low construction cost. The construction cost of house is low in this area because the construction materials are available. The labour cost is cheap in this area. See Appendix-D, Table D11.

5.3.4 Socio-political factors:

Some Socio-political factors are identified in this study. Among them, social security, for living owns home, social network are very important.

Figure 5.6: Percentile distribution of different socio-political factors for settlement

Source: Field survey, 2005

a) Social security: People always want social security for living in a community. About 38% of the total respondents considered social security for settling here. They are mainly from Hindu community.

b) For living own home: It is a general psychology that people want to live his own home. The people who live in Khulna city in rental houses, they always want to take this advantage. To live in own home also increase social status. About 24% respondents consider it for settling here.

c) Social network: A social network developed within the rural people. Sachibunia is a rural area so this factor is responsible for settlement expansion. The social networks develop through business/economic linkages, religious linkage. This factor attracted the new settlers.

d) Post election violence (past residence): Some cases are found that the settlers were suffering for post election violence at their previous residence, specially weaker and under privilege group. They left their past residence and came Sachibunia due to social security and networks.

There are some minor socio-political factors. They are as like- Available inherited land (Kinship), Being localized due to living long time (teacher, domestic labours), and Political problem (past residence). See Appendix-D, Table D12.

5.3.5 Environmental factors:

Additional factors influencing rural residential expansion are the perceived qualities and amenities associated with a new location and may include the perception of a quality environment, a good place to raise children, a better overall quality of life and the perception of rurality and a rural lifestyle (Duke: 2003: 34). The Sachibunia is basically a rural area and the environmental factors are also identified as pull factors influencing settlement expansion.

Figure 5.7 Percentile distribution of different environmental factors for settlement expansion

Source: Field survey , 2005

a) Better living environment: It is a leading factor in all environmental factors. The rural area is better for living, because of open space and pollution free environment. Also in Sachibunia all those facilities are available for better living.

b) Flood free area: This area is highly built up land so free from flood. It is important factor for settlement expansion during 1970s and 1980s. Then farmer’s families settled in this area.

c) *Good soil quality*: Some polders were developed during early 60s in Khulna region. Sachibunia is located polder no 28/2. So this area is protected from the saline water

5.4 CONCLUSION

There are five category of responsible factors are identified in this study. But the physical and economic factors were more responsible for expansion of settlement according to the opinion of the respondent. There are also some others factors which are contributed for rapid expansion of settlement. The developments of Rupsha by pass road, the establishment of Khulna University and others institutions also played a great role. So the expansion of settlement is continuing rapidly. It is making more pressure on agricultural land. Now, it is need to manage the expansion of settlements in a planned way so that the optimum utilization of land will ensure.

6.1 SUMMARY FINDINGS

After all the discussions, it is found that the settlement was expanded rapidly in the last fifteen years. For expansion of settlement some responsible factors were identified. All the responsible factors are categorized as i) Demographic, ii) Physical, iii) Economic, iv) Socio-political and v) Environmental. On the basis of the entire findings and analysis some summary findings/key message can be given. The summary findings/key messages are given here on decadal basis.

a) From 1971-1980:

- In the period only natural expansion of settlement was taken place.
- The demographic factors were predominant because settlement was expanded only for increase in household member and size.
- More than 70% families were involved in farming occupation so the economic base was agriculture.

b) From 1981-1990:

- In 1985, the Khulna-Batiaghata highway was developed.
- In that period the service man, workers, business man, van/rickshaw pullers were established homestead more.
- The socio-political factors were predominant in that period. The social security was a very important social factor. Specially, for the Hindu community.

c) From 1991-2000:

- The internal roads were developed in that period. In 1995, 1km road was developed as *pacca* and 0.5km HBB road developed in 1997.
- The REB was introduced electricity in that period of the study area.
- The Khulna University and Gollamary bazar, different private housing projects, other institutions were developed in that period which have some impact on settlement expansion of the village.
- The average annual growth rate was 3.82 unit in that period.
- The occupational pattern was converted from farming to non-farming.
- The physical factors were influenced the settlement expansion.

d) From 2001-2005:

- The by-pass road was developed in this period which has some impact on settlement expansion.
- In the period, the average annual growth rate was 5.2 unit which is indicated more expansion of settlement.
- The occupational pattern was rapidly changed from agricultural to non-agricultural.
- The physical and economic factors were more responsible for settlement expansion. The low land value was very important economic factor.
- In the period, the lower and middle income city people were settled more.

6.2 CONCLUSION

A ribbon type of settlement has developed in the study area. In the earlier period it was not so dense. But now, more new homesteads have developed along the road side.

In the earlier period the settlements were formed by the farmer families. At that period the area of the settlement was very small. In 1970s the settlement area was 5.12 acres, but after 35 years in 2005 the settlement area has become 15.27 acres. For this rapid expansion of settlement there are five categories responsible factors were identified. The physical and economic factors were more responsible for the expansion of settlement according to the opinion of the respondent. Without these factors there are also some factors which are not mentioned here. But they are also responsible for rapid expansion of settlement in the study area. The development of by pass road plays a great impact for the expansion of settlement. The establishment of Khulna university, others institutions have some influence for expansion of settlement in Sachibunia village (See Appendix-D: map D1).

In future some study can be done in the study area such as the changing pattern FAR, quality of settlement which was not covered by this study. The present study was conducted only with the pull factors of settlement expansion. But the push factors were not considered. So, some study may be conducted with the push factors of

settlement expansion. The present study is helpful for different organizations to providing necessary information about the trend of settlement expansion and its responsible factors. This is also helpful for planned expansion of rural settlements.

The expansion of settlement is continuing rapidly in this area. It makes more pressure on agricultural land. As a result, with the reduction of farmland agricultural production will hamper in future. Now it needs to guide and control the expansion of settlements in a way so that the optimum utilization of land will be ensured.

APPENDIX -A

Questionnaire for Study of Rural Settlement Expansion Pattern

(A Case Study of Sachibunia Village Under Batiaghata Upazila in Khulna District)

Urban and Rural Planning Discipline

Khulna University, Khulna

(All the information will be collected for study purpose only and kept secret)

1. ID NO: **2. Plot no:** **3. Name of Para:**

4. NAME OF THE RESPONDENT:

5. IDENTIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENT (AGED PEOPLE):

Age	Sex	Occupation		Expenditure	Income/month (tk)		Education	Religion	Marital status
		Primary	Secondary		Primary	Secondary			

*A. Sex: 1-Male, 2-Female;

*B. Education: 1-Signature only, 2-Primary, 3-Secondary, 4-S.S.C, 5-H.S.C, 6-Degree, 7-Degree +, 8-Others, 9-Illiterate

*C. Religion: 1-Hindu, 2-Muslim, 3-Christan, 4-others;

*D. Marital status: 1-Marrid, 2-Unmarrid, 3-Divorsed, 4-Widow

6. INFORMATION ABOUT HOUSEHOLD

SL	Age	Sex	Occupation		Income/month (TK)		Education	Marital status
			Primary	Secondary	Primary	Secondary		
M ₁								
M ₂								
M ₃								
M ₄								
M ₅								
M ₆								
M ₇								
M ₈								

*A. Sex: 1-Male, 2-Female;

*B. Education: 1-Signature only, 2-Primary, 3-Secondary, 4-S.S.C, 5-H.S.C, 6-Degree, 7-Degree +, 8-Others, 9-Illiterate

*C. Religion: 1-Hindu, 2-Muslim, 3-Christan, 4-others;

*D. Marital status: 1-Marrid, 2-Unmarrid, 3-Divorsed, 4-Widow

7. INFORMATION ABOUT HOME ESTABLISHMENT

I. Year of establishment of existing homestead:

II. Existing area of homestead (Decimal):

III. Who was come to the area at first for house establishment?.....

IV. Where was your/his origin/root?

V. What were the causes for home establishment? (Show the percentage in the boxes)

1. Demographic 2. Physical 3. Economic 4. Socio-political 5. Environmental

A. If demographic then, what are the causes?

Increase of household size

Migration

Specify:.....

B. If Physical then, what are the causes?

I. Good infrastructure facilities

II. Transport accessibility

III. Land available for housing

IV. Specify:.....

C. If Economic then, what are the causes?

- I. For getting better employment opportunity
- II. Low land value
- III. Availability of construction materials
- IV. Specify:.....

D. If Socio-political then, what are the causes?

- I. Safety social life
- II. Social believes
- III. Social norms
- IV. Specify:.....

E. If Environmental then, what are the causes?

- Flood free area
- Good soil quality
- Good water quality
- Better living environment
- Specify:.....

8. INFORMATION ABOUT HOMESTEAD LAND (Only who established homestead from 1971-2005):

A. Previous land use: 1) Agricultural 2) Homestead 3) Water body 4) Others (specify).....

B. Source of land for home establishment: 1) By bought 2) Gifted 3) Inherited

C. If buy then, 1) Year:..... 2) Land value (TK):

9. INFORMATION ABOUT PHYSICAL CONDITION:

A. Adjacent road Condition

Type of road	Distance (ft)	Width (ft)

*Type of road: 1-Paved, 2-Katcha,3-HBB

B. House condition

HOUSE TYPE	Construction materials		
	Floor	Wall	Roof

*House type:1- Building, 2-Semi-pacca, 3-Katcha

*Floor, wall, roof materials: 1-Mud, 2-Concrete, 3-Brick, 4-Jute, 5-Golpata, 6-Sugarcan, 7-Straw,8-Tail,9-Tin ,10- Others.

10. INFORMATION ABOUT LAND

A. Land ownership pattern: Land owner Landless Land leaseholder

If land owner, then

Year	Total homestead area (Decimal)	Land under agricultural use (Decimal)
1971-75		
1976-80		
1981-85		
1986-90		
1991-95		
1995-2000		
2001-05		

11. Put your comments about settlement expansion in this village

.....

Signature of the surveyor

Survey Date:.....

.....

List of components which important for settlement expansion

(Make open discussion with the key personals on these components)

1. Rural road:

Type

Construction years

Construction authority/agency

Year of road development

Road development agency

Impact of road development on settlement expansion

2. Growth centre:

Type

Year of introduction

Distance from the village

Activity performed in the GC

Impact of GC on settlement expansion

3. Electricity:

Year of introduction

Providing agency

Monthly cost

Satisfactory level

Impact of electricity on settlement expansion

4. School:

Type, Location

Year of establishment

Number of students

Satisfactory level

Impact of school on settlement expansion

5. Migration:

Type, Starting Year, Destination
Religion of Migrate people
Income level
Causes for migration
Effect of migration on settlement expansion

6. Safe drinking water and sanitation:

Source , number of tube well ,Introduction period
Providing authority
Availability
Role on settlement expansion

7.Land market:

Land value
Buyers and sellers
Their religion and income level
Role of land market on settlement expansion

8.Economic activity:

Type
Employment changing pattern
Agricultural production
Technologies in agricultural production
Dominate economic activity

9.Important infrastructures:

Type
Location
Year of establishment

APPENDIX-B
COORDINATION SCHEMA

Objective 1. To explore the trend of settlement expansion from 1971 to 2005.

INDICATORS	COMPLEX VARIABLE	SIMPLE VARIABLE	VALUE/UNIT
Rural settlement and Pattern	Trend of settlement expansion	Type of expansion	Clustered, random, regular
		Direction	Along road/river/canal
		Rate of expansion	Area coverage, acre
		Preferred land	Area coverage
		Periodical expansion	Mapping, Acre
	Settlement Pattern representing factors	Density of settlement	No. HH/area, High, Low
		Spacing	Area/no of settlement
		Housing structure	Katcha / Pacca
		Area coverage	Acre, Percentage
		Nature and extent	Percentile, time, event

Objective 2. To identify the causal factors of settlements expansion in the study area.

INDICATORS	COMPLEX VARIABLE	SIMPLE VARIABLE	VALUE/UNIT
Demographic Cause	Demographic factor	Population growth	No Per year
		Household size	Frequency
		Age structure	Frequency
		Migration rate	Frequency/year
		Birth rate	Frequency
Physical cause	Effect of rural road	Length, width, type	KM, m, pave/Katcha
		Effect of G. centre	Distance, cost, time
		Housing condition	Status of house
		Analysis of services	Utility facility
Economic Causes	Income structure	Increase of income	Currency
		Change of employment	Job type, nature
		Land value	Type, location, price
		Agricultural Change	Intensity, production
Social causes	Social change	Social believe	Type
		Marital status	Frequency
		Religion, culture	Type
		Social norms	Type
Environmental	Natural opportunities	Flood free area	Acre
		Natural migration	percentile

APPENDIX-C

TYPES OF SETTLEMENTS

According to A. Baqee (1998), the settlements of Bangladesh can be categorise mainly three different types. They are given with definition and layout.

1. Dispersed settlements: A unit where only two of three houses are build for living one or two families 5/7 number of family member. These types of settlements are located for taking advantage of farm lands. In Bangladesh, these type of settlements are seen at all the flood-plain area. These also get in Rangpur and Dinajpur of north Bengal.

2. Gathered settlements: When the settlements are taking a large shape by locating one beside another then that is called gathered settlement. These types of settlements are also classified in three sub-categories.

A. Liner settlements: Generally linear settlements are called that type of settlements where elements are arrange in a way that it look like a chain. Sometimes it can be spread 5-6 miles. But the density are not equal everywhere. These types of settlements are formed along the rivers, roads. In Bangladesh this type of settlements are formed along the river bank.

B. Nucleated settlements: For different types of advantages and disadvantages the settlements are located at aggregated form, these are called nucleated settlements. These types of settlements are small in size. It is formed for some natural and social factor. these are found in hoar and baor region and sylhet.

C. Centred settlements: These are another type of nucleated settlements. These types of settlements are located at compacted form. A service or institution is situated at the centre of the settlement. For the formation of this type of settlement the natural factors are more responsible. These types are seen in Mymensing, Kisorgonj, Dhaka district etc.

3. Isolated settlements: Isolated settlements are as like dispersed settlements. Isolated settlements are also called isolated house. In Bangladesh these types of settlement are seen in hilly region like Chittagong hilltracks where the tribe people are living. Also seen in Haluaghat, Rangpur-Dinajpur border area. In sort, it can be said that this types are seen in remote area.

APPENDIX-D

SOME IMPORTANT DATA

Table D1: Primary occupation of the settlers

Primary occupation of HH head	Year of home stead establishment								
	Before 1971	1971-80		1981-90		1991-2000		2001-05	
	Base year	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF
Farmer	30	13	43	10	53	5	58	6	64
Business	0	1	1	0	1	7	8	4	12
Service	3	2	5	2	7	8	15	8	23
Teacher	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	1	5
Shopkeeper	2	0	2	0	2	2	4	2	6
Doctor	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
Carpenter	3	4	7	0	7	1	8	0	8
Van/Rickshaw puller	0	1	1	2	3	4	7	3	10
Day labour	1	1	2	3	5	4	9	2	11
Driver	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	2
Shrimp farming	0	0	0	3	3	1	4	0	4
Total	39	22	61	21	82	38	120	26	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D2: Family income level of the settlers in different years

Family income/month	Year of home stead establishment								
	Before 1971	1971-80		1981-90		1991-2000		2001-05	
	Base year	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF
Below 2000	2	0	2	1	3	3	6	0	6
2001-4000	9	10	19	8	27	16	43	13	56
4001-6000	19	12	31	9	40	15	55	10	65
6001-8000	6	0	6	1	7	2	9	3	12
Above 8000	3	0	3	2	5	2	7	0	7
Total	39	22	61	21	82	38	120	26	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D3: Religious status of the settlers in different years

Year	Religion type		Total
	Hindu	Muslim	
Before 1971	39	0	39
1971-80	19	3	22
1981-90	19	2	21
1991-2000	21	17	38
2001-05	15	11	26
Total	113	33	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D5: Previous use of land where settlement establishment in different year

Land use category	Year of homestead establishment							
	1971-1980		1981-1990		1991-2000		2001-05	
	F		F	CF	F	CF	F	CF
Agricultural	15		15	30	22	52	17	69
Homestead	5		4	9	12	21	7	28
Water body	2		2	4	4	8	2	10
Total	22		21	43	38	81	27	107

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D6: Source of land for settlement establishment in different year

Source of land	Frequency of HH in different years							
	1971-1980		1981-1990		1991-2000		2001-05	
	F		F	CF	F	CF	F	CF
By purchase	9		12	21	33	54	18	54
Gifted	1		1	2	2	4	4	4
Inherited	12		8	20	3	23	4	23
Total	22		21	43	38	81	26	107

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D7: Agricultural Land ownership pattern in different year.

Ownership pattern	Year of homestead establishment									
	Before 1971		1971-80		1981-90		1991-2000		2001-05	
	F		F	CF	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF
Land owner	29		10	39	10	49	9	58	3	61
Landless	2		5	7	5	12	24	36	18	54
Land lease holder	8		7	15	6	21	5	26	5	31
Total	39		22	61	21	82	38	120	26	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D8: Status of factors for settlement establishment in different years

Factors	Factors of homestead establishment (scores)				
	Demographic	Physical	Economic	Socio-political	Environmental
Before 1971	38	63	147	82	60
1971-1980	34	42	53	43	43
1981-1990	23	60	103	35	27
1991-2000	21	121	123	44	62
2001-05	15	89	55	52	43
Total	131	375	481	256	235

Source: Field survey, August 2005, Every 10 % = 1 (Suppose)

Table D9: Demographical factors for settlement formation in different year

Priority	Factors	Year of homestead establishment				
		Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05
1	Increase of household size	5	4	5	4	3
	In Migration	2	4	0	1	0
	Total	7	8	5	5	3
2	Increase of household size	0	4	0	1	0
	In Migration	3	0	0	0	0
	Total	3	4	0	1	0

Source: Field survey, August 2005

TableD10: Physical factors for settlement formation in different year

Priority	Physical factors	Year of homestead establishment				
		Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05
1	Good infrastructure facilities	1	2	1	2	2
	Availability of transport	0	1	0	7	8
	Land available of housing	7	3	2	9	5
	Proximity to Service centres	1	0	0	0	1
	Near to city	3	4	11	4	4
	House acquired for by pass road	0	0	0	2	0
	Proximity to working place	1	1	1	2	0
Total	13	11	15	26	20	
2	Availability of transport	2	1	5	4	2
	Proximity to Service centres	1	0	0	1	0
	Near to city	1	0	0	4	3
	Proximity to working place	0	0	1	0	0
	Total	4	1	6	9	5

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D11: Economic factors for settlement formation in different year

Priority	Economic factors	Year of homestead establishment				
		Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05
1	Low land value	9	1	3	16	7
	Low construction cost	0	0	0	1	0
	Low travel time and cost	5	4	3	8	3
	For better income (salon, retail...)	2	3	2	3	5
	Land available for farming	12	7	4	1	0
Total	28	12	15	29	15	
2	Low land value	4	1	1	0	0
	Low travel time and cost	0	0	1	0	0
	Total	4	1	2	0	0

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D12: Socio-political factors for settlement formation in different year

Priority	Socio-political factors	Year of homestead establishment				
		Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05
1	Social security	13	6	5	5	1
	Being localized due to living long time	2	1	0	0	1
	Social network	0	2	1	2	3
	political problem (past residence)	1	0	1	2	1
	post election violence (past residence)	0	0	1	1	1
	Available inherited land (Kinship)	2	4	1	1	0
	For living own home	3	0	0	6	9
Total	21	13	9	17	16	
2	Social security	0	0	1	1	2
	Localised due to living long time	0	0	0	1	0
	Social network	1	0	0	0	0
	political problem (past residence)	0	0	0	2	0
	Available inherited land (Kinship)	0	2	1	1	0
	For living own home	0	0	0	1	1
	Total	1	2	2	6	3

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D13: Environmental factors for settlement formation in different year

Priority	Environmental factors	Year of homestead establishment				
		Before 1971	1971-80	1981-90	1991-2000	2001-05
1	Flood free area	6	4	1	2	1
	Good soil quality	4	2	1	0	0
	Better living environment	10	6	7	16	10
	Total	20	12	9	18	11
2	Good soil quality	4	1	0	2	0
	Better living environment	1	1	1	0	1
	Total	5	2	1	2	1

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D14: Changing pattern of land value Per decimal (TK)

Land type		Land value in different year (TK)				
		1970	1980	1990	2000	2005
Agricultural	Western portion	500	1000	3000	4000	6000
	Eastern portion	2000	4000	8000	18000	20000
Homestead	Western portion	1000	2000	6000	8000	10000
	Eastern portion	3000	5000	10000	20000	22000

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D15: Place of origin by year of homestead establishment

Place of origin	Year of homestead establishment								
	Before 1971	1971-80		1981-90		1991-2000		2001-05	
	Base year	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF	F	CF
Bagarhat	1	0	1	1	2	4	6	2	8
Barisal	1	1	2	1	3	2	5	0	5
Batiaghata	20	5	25	7	32	6	38	5	43
Sachibunia	5	4	9	5	14	4	18	3	21
Dumuria	0	5	5	2	7	2	9	1	10
Khulna city	0	0	0	3	3	13	16	12	28
Gopalganj	4	0	4	0	4	3	7	0	7
Jessore	7	3	10	0	10	1	11	0	11
Koyra	1	0	1	2	3	2	5	0	5
Pirojpur	0	2	2	0	2	0	2	0	2
Rupsha	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Sariatpur	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
Satkhira	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Dakop	0	2	2	0	2	0	2	0	2
Total	39	22	61	21	82	38	120	26	146

Source: Field survey, August 2005

Table D16: Relation between responsible factors and family income level

Family income per month		Responsible factors for settlement expansion				
		Demographic	Physical	Economic	Socio-political	Environmental
1-2000	HH	2	4	4	1	3
	%	14.2	28.5	28.5	7.1	21.4
2001-4000	HH	13	33	38	31	25
	%	9.2	23.6	27.1	22.14	17.8
4001-6000	HH	11	40	43	34	32
	%	6.8	25	26.8	21.2	20
6001-8000	HH	1	5	9	5	7
	%	3.7	18.5	33.3	18.5	25.9
Above 8000	HH	1	3	5	5	3
	%	5.8	17.6	29.4	29.4	17.6

Source: Field survey, August 2005

APPENDIX-E
SOME EQUATION

E1. Average annual growth rate: The housing growth rate is calculated by following equation.

$$\frac{\text{Increase number of housing units (Hinc)}}{\text{Number of year (Yn)}}$$

E2. Housing density: The housing density is calculated by following equation.

$$\frac{\text{Total Number of housing units (Hn)}}{\text{Total homestead area (Ha)}}$$

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